

Legal Considerations in Informed Consent: Disclosing Statistical Mortality Information to Late-Stage Cancer Patients

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Abstract

Physicians have a duty to ensure informed consent is achieved to respect patient autonomy but guidelines about the specific details required for informed consent remain situational, nebulous, and may vary by jurisdiction. In addition to the harm to patients, failures in informed consent can carry severe legal consequences for physicians. This commentary examines the legal considerations surrounding the disclosure of statistical mortality information to late-stage cancer patients within the context of informed consent in contemporary medical practice. Beginning with an exploration of the evolution of informed consent following *Canterbury v Spence*, this discussion underscores the transition from a professional-centered to a patient-centered approach. Surveys of medical oncologists indicate large variation in practice standards of communicating prognostic information, and most oncologists believed formal training in this communication is both necessary and yet was insufficient in their education. While accurate and precise prognostic information holds undeniable utility for patients, patient understanding of prognostic medical information is subject to numerous biases and may be further complicated by levels of statistical literacy. The precedent set in *Arato v Avedon* ruled that statistical mortality information is not always required for informed consent, but this analysis highlights certain situations in which disclosure of such information by physicians may be legally required. These situations may become more prevalent as medical science advances, and this commentary provides informed consent guidelines that uphold legal obligations for medical practitioners, to facilitate shared patient-physician understanding.

Introduction

The doctrine of informed consent in medicine has deep historical roots, stemming from the post-World War II Nuremberg Code, which was crafted to prevent the exploitation of individuals in unethical medical experiments. This doctrine is grounded in the fundamental principle that individuals have the right to decide what medical procedures may be performed on their bodies, [1] a corollary of the right to bodily autonomy. Violations of this right thus expose physicians to potential medical malpractice litigation and professional consequences. While informed consent dictates that physicians must provide patients with sufficient information to make informed decisions about their healthcare, strict definitions of the type and quantity of information disclosed are not present in applicable law. This article explores the nuances of informed consent, with a particular focus on the extent to which physicians are required to disclose statistical mortality information to late-stage cancer patients. This analysis aims to guide physicians in navigating the delicate balance between patient autonomy and professional standards when disclosing information to ensure that patients can make well-informed choices regarding their medical care.

Informed Consent before *Canterbury v Spence*

Prior to the 1970s, U.S. judicial courts held that a physician's duty to provide information was dictated by the standard of care. [2] This standard was heavily dependent upon the setting of informed consent, for standards of care are different across hospitals of disparate resources, between medical specialties, and for distinct cultures of care within communities. Accordingly, determination of this standard in court was reliant upon expert testimony. This system heavily favored physicians in medical malpractice cases, as physicians were wary of testifying against colleagues. In addition, this system provided limited legal recourse for inadequate information disclosures, provided the level of disclosure was not dissimilar to that of other physicians in similar clinical settings.

In 1972, *Canterbury v Spence* instituted a paradigm shift in medical informed consent. [3] Rather than relying on the professional standard of care, the *Canterbury* case ruled that informed consent required disclosure of information that would be important to a reasonable person. [3] This relies less on expert testimony, and rather invites the jury to imagine whether a reasonable patient in the community would consider the information material to medical decisions. [3] In practice, this shift often meant physicians were required to disclose more information to facilitate informed consent, and since 1972, additional cases have debated the precise details that are necessary to disclose to a reasonable patient. [4–6] Currently, states are divided in their use of the traditional professional standard for disclosure versus the patient-centered standard pioneered in the *Canterbury* case; the latter is discussed below.

Canterbury v Spence: the landmark case in informed consent

Jerry Canterbury was a 19-year-old clerk who presented to clinic with severe back pain. [3] At the advice of his neurosurgeon, Dr. William T. Spence, Canterbury underwent a laminectomy in 1958. [3] Unbeknownst to Canterbury, laminectomies have approximately a one percent chance of causing paralysis. [3] After the surgery and a subsequent fall in the hospital, Canterbury was left paralyzed below the waist and incontinent. [3]

Canterbury sued on the grounds of negligence, alleging that he had not been adequately informed of the risks associated with the procedure. [3] The pivotal legal aspect of this case emerged during the 1968 trial when the defense argued that Canterbury's lack of expert testimony should prevent the case from proceeding. [3] However, Judge Spottswood W. Robinson III of the DC Circuit Court allowed the case to go to a jury, establishing a standard for informed consent based on what a reasonable patient would want to know, rendering expert testimony unnecessary. [3]

While the jury ultimately ruled against Canterbury, this case instituted a shift from the professional practice standard. [3] The *Canterbury* case ruled that a reasonable person would want to know, and hence physicians should be required to disclose, the following information: 1) the diagnosis,

2) a description of the nature and purpose of the proposed treatment, 3) the anticipated results of the treatment, and any serious risks or complications, and 4) the nature and risks of treatment alternatives or refusal. [3] This list notably does not explicitly include statistical mortality information – the subject of this commentary – but such information could arguably be required under points 3) and 4). Namely, the proposed treatment may be anticipated to result in a more favorable mortality prognosis than other treatments or withholding treatment, while complications may result in an increased mortality rate. These four guidelines have also been supported in subsequent medical malpractice cases, such as *Nixdorf v Hicken* and *Truman v Thomas*, [4,5] and additional guidelines have been identified in cases such as *Gates v Jenson*, which ruled that physicians are required to disclose personal interests that may influence their judgment. [6] Case law has also identified disclosures that are not required for informed consent, such as risks that are common knowledge, risks that the patient already knows, or other information that would not affect the patient’s medical decisions. [7] Notably, the Canterbury standard for informed consent is personalized in two ways: 1) if the patient is already knowledgeable about the treatment, then they demand fewer disclosures, and 2) a physician must additionally explain unique information such as benefits or risks that may be significant to a particular patient.

Exemptions to the *Canterbury* standard for informed consent exist in medical emergencies, and when information disclosure is likely to cause significant emotional harm to a patient. [8] The latter consideration may be relevant to the disclosure of mortality information to cancer patients, as such information could be damaging to a patient’s psychological health. [9] However, likely due to the innate challenges in evaluating the probability and extent of significant psychological distress following potential information disclosure, such an exemption is transient and hence more relevant to the acute management of diseases, and less relevant to the discussions of long-term care and prognosis that often occur in cancer management. In the absence of these exceptions, the utility of statistical mortality information to late-stage cancer patients must be examined in order to evaluate its legal implications under the *Canterbury standard*.

The utility of statistical mortality information in informed consent

The disclosure of statistical mortality information to cancer patients is debatable between medical oncologists. In a survey of over one thousand physicians, while 98% said that they will tell patients that their condition is terminal, oncologists are divided in either always disclosing prognostic information, or only doing so if their patient indicates their desire for a more quantitative prognosis. [9] In addition, 73% of responders indicated prognosis communication education was inadequate during their training, despite almost all responders believing it should be part of oncologist training. [9] This status quo raises potential issues for states which follow professional standards for disclosures in informed consent, as a single professional standard is lacking, hindering a clear resolution. Patient preferences in the level of quantitative detail delivered during the communication of their prognosis may also vary, which limits the “reasonable person” standard initiated by the *Canterbury* case.

Importantly, informed consent requires not just the mere disclosure of medical information by physicians, but also information must be presented in a simplified manner that is understandable to patients without a medical background. Patient comprehension varies based on the method of information delivery, [10] and can be improved by novel teaching strategies at the cost of a prolonged informed consent process. [11] Following information disclosures, patients often retain mistaken beliefs about the benefits of procedures, [12] indicating that methods of communication must be improved so as not to waste physician resources and time. Statistical mortality information may be more complex than qualitative information about the benefits of a treatment, and hence may be even more difficult to communicate to patients effectively. For example, oncology therapeutics are often supported by clinical

trial data using early efficacy endpoints, including the objective response rate and progression-free survival, and these endpoints do not always correlate with overall survival. [12] Communicating such nuances to manage patient expectations may present a challenge for providers, particularly in health systems where appointment slots are of fixed duration. Indeed, failures of informed consent arising from patient misconceptions (potentially due to ineffective provider communication) may contribute to disastrous consequences including performing surgery on the wrong patient. [14]

Additional obstacles to informed consent also arise that may be more specific to the disclosure of prognostic mortality information. In the context of late-stage cancer patients, it is often difficult for oncologists to accurately predict a patient's prognosis, making the disclosure of such information infeasible. [15] Moreover, the disclosure of statistical mortality information may not facilitate patient understanding, even when providers are confident of a bleak prognosis. In studies of stage IV cancer patients who were told a prognosis of one year or less, patients exhibited optimism bias, illusion of superiority, and other biases exacerbated by higher levels of hope assessed using the Health Hope Index. [16,17] More hopeful patients reported estimated survival of over 4 years longer than less hopeful patients and were more likely to mistakenly believe their treatment was curative rather than palliative. [16,17] Data are mixed regarding whether increased hope affects patient survival, but increased hope is linked to greater rates of healthcare utilization, potentially indicating overtreatment. [16,17]

Set in a status quo where physicians may neglect to mention serious risks associated with medical procedures, the patient-centered standard initiated in the Canterbury case aimed primarily for the disclosure of the existence of risks. [3] The disclosure of prognostic benefits, such as life expectancy, associated with distinct courses of treatment was a secondary goal, and the Canterbury case makes no explicit argument for or against providing quantitative estimates of the incidence of adverse outcomes. [3] While this omission could have been a strategic decision by the plaintiff's attorney, it also suggests that the court did not believe quantitative information was sufficiently salient to be material to the decisions of the "reasonable patient." [3] Patient preferences and understanding may vary based on patient factors such as education and emotional state, as well as the level of certainty associated with the information. Indeed, while one could argue that many Americans would have sufficient statistical literacy to understand point estimates of life expectancy, far fewer patients (and potentially physicians) would understand the confidence interval or credible interval that articulate the level of variance associated with the estimate – an integral characteristic of the estimate. For example, a patient may evaluate a hypothetical treatment that is guaranteed to extend their life by one year differently versus a more variable treatment that has a 50% chance of extending their life by four years and a 50% chance of shortening their life by two years. Both hypothetical treatments produce a mean increase in life expectancy by one year, and yet may be drastically different in outcome, emphasizing the importance of understanding the variance of estimates for making medical decisions. Despite these challenges, however, the utility of a shared patient-provider understanding of low-variance prognostic information is undeniable; a precise understanding of prognosis would provide a reliable timeline for patients to get their affairs in order, which may include organizing finances and custody arrangements for their children. While the barriers to reaching such an understanding have been described above, these barriers do not absolve modern physicians of the ethical responsibility to facilitate patient autonomy, [18] potentially by educating patients on statistical literacy, or by using qualitative terms to indicate risk (e.g., "rarely" or "usually").

The debate surrounding the disclosure of statistical mortality information to cancer patients reflects the complexities and nuances of informed consent, particularly in late-stage cases where

standardized guidelines to ensure effective and ethical patient-physician communication in these challenging situations.

Arato v Avedon: statistical life expectancy is not required for informed consent

The case of *Arato v Avedon* delves into the complex issue of whether physicians should disclose statistical mortality information to cancer patients. [19] Miklos Arato was diagnosed with pancreatic cancer in 1980 and filled out a routine patient questionnaire indicating his desire to be told the truth about his condition. However, Mr. Arato never directly asked his physicians about his prognosis, and his treating physicians did not disclose the high statistical mortality rates associated with pancreatic cancer. While Mr. Arato's physicians recommended a course of chemotherapy and radiation, Mr. Arato eventually succumbed to cancer. Subsequently, Mr. Arato's family filed a lawsuit against his physicians, alleging that they failed to adequately disclose the potential ineffectiveness of the treatment, leading to Mr. Arato's suffering and financial losses.

Mr. Arato's treating physicians cited various reasons for their decision not to disclose specific statistical life expectancy data to their patient. They pointed to Mr. Arato's significant anxiety, suggesting that disclosure of specific prognostic information could have worsened Mr. Arato's psychological health. Additionally, the physicians argued that relying on statistical data alone was not appropriate for informing a patient's prognosis, as it failed to account for the individualized symptoms, medical history, and character traits that could significantly affect the course of the disease. Accordingly, they argued, statistical life expectancy would not be material to a reasonable patient described in the *Canterbury* case. In addition, expert testimony indicated that the standard of practice did not require disclosure of statistical life expectancy. The superior court ruled in favor of the physicians, emphasizing the unreliability of statistical data when applied to individual cases.

Current legal considerations for physicians

Through the examination of the *Canterbury* case, *Arato v Avedon*, and the questionable utility of statistical life expectancy to advanced cancer patients, this analysis concludes that disclosure of statistical mortality information may be legally required when 1) it is common practice for physicians in that setting, in jurisdictions that apply the professional standard for information disclosure, or 2) the physician believes that statistical mortality information is of particular value to the patient, in jurisdictions that abide by the *Canterbury* standard for informed consent. During a lawsuit, jurisdictional considerations determine whether the outcome of such cases will be determined by expert testimony (in the former situation) or by lay jurors (in the latter situation). While the legal standard described in the *Canterbury* case does not necessarily require the disclosure of statistical mortality information, [3] exemplified by *Arato v Avedon*, [19] physicians may still aim to follow ethical guidelines to facilitate patient understanding of prognosis, as an extension of considerations of patient autonomy. [18]

Legally, physicians will be protected so long as they disclose prognostic information to a similar extent to how they were taught or to their colleagues, or when it is indicated that the information is of particular interest based on patient particulars – most evidently, when a patient asks for the prognostic information. In the span of the intricacies of the doctor-patient relationship, these are relatively straightforward guidelines for physicians to follow.

These guidelines may evolve as medical science advances. For example, if physicians were able to predict prognostic outcomes for individual patients to high accuracy, or if statistical literacy increases in patient populations, then this information could become material to a reasonable patient; the *Canterbury* standard may then compel physicians to disclose this information. This would increase the burden on physicians both regarding information disclosures, and regarding the level of required understanding of each of their patients. Effective guidelines on informed consent are required to facilitate effective clinical practice, where the knowledgeable physician must work alongside their patient to aid them in making decisions that facilitate their health and wellbeing.

References

1. Schloendorff v. Society of New York Hospital, 211 N.Y. 125, 105 N.E. 92 (N.Y. 1914).
2. DiFilippo v. Preston, 53 Del. 539, 173 A.2d 333 (Del. 1961).
3. Canterbury v Spence, 464 F.2d 772, 775 (DC Cir 1972).
4. Nixdorf v. Hicken, 612 P.2d 348 (Utah 1980).
5. Truman v Thomas, 27 Cal. 3d 285, 611 P.2d 902 (Cal. 1980).
6. Gates v Jenson, 92 Wash. 2d 246, 595 P.2d 919 (Wash. 1979).
7. Paterick TJ, Carson GV, Allen MC, Paterick TE. Medical Informed Consent: General Considerations for Physicians. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*. 2008;83(3):313-319. doi:10.4065/83.3.313
8. Cornfeldt v Tongen, 262 N.W.2d 684 (Minn. 1977).
9. Daugherty CK, Hlubocky FJ. What Are Terminally Ill Cancer Patients Told About Their Expected Deaths? A Study of Cancer Physicians' Self-Reports of Prognosis Disclosure. *JCO*. 2008;26(36):5988-5993. doi:10.1200/JCO.2008.17.2221
10. Schenker Y, Meisel A. Informed consent in clinical care: practical considerations in the effort to achieve ethical goals. *JAMA*. 2011;305(11):1130-1131. doi:10.1001/jama.2011.333
11. Fink AS, Prochazka AV, Henderson WG, et al. Enhancement of surgical informed consent by addition of repeat back: a multicenter, randomized controlled clinical trial. *Ann Surg*. 2010;252(1):27-36. doi:10.1097/SLA.0b013e3181e3ec61
12. Merino M, Kasamon Y, Theoret M, Pazdur R, Kluetz P, Gormley N. Irreconcilable Differences: The Divorce Between Response Rates, Progression-Free Survival, and Overall Survival. *JCO*. 2023;41(15):2706-2712. doi:10.1200/JCO.23.00225
13. Rothberg MB, Sivalingam SK, Ashraf J, et al. Patients' and cardiologists' perceptions of the benefits of percutaneous coronary intervention for stable coronary disease. *Ann Intern Med*. 2010;153(5):307-313. doi:10.7326/0003-4819-153-5-201009070-00005
14. Chassin MR, Becher EC. The wrong patient. *Ann Intern Med*. 2002;136(11):826-833. doi:10.7326/0003-4819-136-11-200206040-00012
15. Nahm SH, Martin AJ, Clayton JM, et al. Accuracy of oncologists' estimates of expected survival time in advanced cancer. *JNCI Cancer Spectrum*. 2023;7(6):pkad094. doi:10.1093/jncics/pkad094
16. Chay J, Huynh VA, Cheung YB, et al. The relationship between hope, medical expenditure and survival among advanced cancer patients. *Front Psychol*. 2023;14:1151976. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1151976
17. Finkelstein EA, Baid D, Cheung YB, et al. Hope, bias and survival expectations of advanced cancer patients: A cross-sectional study. *Psycho-Oncology*. 2021;30(5):780-788. doi:10.1002/pon.5675
18. Beauchamp TL, Childress JF. *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*. 5. ed. Oxford Univ. Press; 2001.
19. Arato v. Avedon, 5 Cal. 4th 1172, 858 P.2d 598 (Cal. 1993).